

OBSERVATION OF PATHOLOGICAL PROCESSES ON THE MUCOUS MEMBRANE OF THE ORAL CAVITY

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Annotation: in this article, the observation of pathological processes in the mucous membrane of the oral cavity, the causes of their origin, types and their effect on the mucous membrane of the oral cavity is sufficiently illuminated.

Keywords: oral cavity, tissues, infectious diseases, clinical signs of diseases, exudation, mucous shell, stain, nodule, nodule, Hawthorn, blister, blister, purulent bladder...

The development of pathological processes on the surface of the mucous membrane of the oral cavity is accompanied by the appearance of wound elements. Relying on the similarity of the origin and morphological signs of elements in different diseases in the main clinical manifestations, all elements of trauma are divided into the following groups by their main symptoms:

- 1) discoloration;
- 2) bounded exudation;
- 3) lining of the mucous membrane;
- 4) tissue swelling;
- 5) chemotic formation on the mucous membrane.

The formation of wound elements on the mucous membrane of the oral cavity and the skin is observed with the formation of elements of the same - monomorphic form, as well as polymorphic elements of different shapes.¹

Therefore, the elements of primary injury and the elements of secondary injury observed as a result of their development are distinguished. Elements of primary injury include spotting, nodule, nodule, Hawthorn, blister, blister, purulent bladder, hardened purulent sac, blister, abscess. Secondary injury elements include erosion, aphthous ulcer, rupture, scarring, carash, cap, to the body, drying of the shell, tumor.

Primary injury elements:

Stain: discoloration of the mucous membrane. Differs in inflammatory and non-inflammatory spots. The stain formed as a result of the inflammatory process is characterized by redness of the clearly delimited part of the tissue.² A roseola is a circular erythematous stain 1.5-2 mm to 10 mm in size with a distinct appearance.

Non-inflammatory spots include hemorrhagic and repellent spots. Depending on the size of the hemorrhagic stain, petechia - dotted and ecchymoses - is a common hemorrhage of oval or circular shape. A carash derivative that occurs from the accumulation of external and internal staining substances depending on the origin of the repellent stain. Spots vary in location and appearance: in the same cases they are clearly delimited, in other cases more common. The

¹ O'.B.Sharapov, Internal Medicine, Abu Ali Ibn Sino Tashkent 1994.

² K.Bakhodirov. Diagnosis and diagnosis in internal diseases, Tashkent 1993.

spots caused by the action of scabies, bismuth and Mercury substances will settle down, forming a border along the edges of the gums. When silver forms carash in the gums, spots appear in a diffuse state, which are not clear in shape. Mutilation can also be observed in the oral cavity in areas other than the gums, such as the corner of the mouth.

A non - hollow derivative of the mucous membrane, which differs in color from the mucous membrane, rises above the surface of the shell-nodule. Its shape varies: the bottom is sharpened, semi-circular, blunt and is observed in other forms.

In some cases, the formation of the papule is observed as a result of an increase in the size of epithelial cells, in other cases as a result of the active participation of specific layers of the mucous membrane. Most often, papules are formed as a result of enlarged epithelia and active, simultaneous participation of specific mucous layers. Nodular rashes appear directly under the influence of inflammation. A typical coin rash for the body - to-body floor of the oral mucosa shell is observed in red flat iron. When the development of the papule is reversed, there are no traces left in its place. Rashes occur from the papule joint. When a node begins to form, a solid derivative appears under the mucous shell. When palpating, a circular, painless infiltrate is detected. The node can purify and form a leakage path or scarring (on the example of poison gum).

A bubble is an element that is formed from a small influx of liquids (exudate, blood); is a hollow element.³ It is located on the surface of the mucous membrane and is 1.5-2mm. from 3-4 mm in size. The walls of the bubble are made up of a thin layer of epithelium, which quickly perforates and forms erosion.

At the time of morphological examination of the elements, it is necessary to identify the elements with the same shape (monomorph rash) or the rash with different shapes (polymorphic rash), paying attention to their symmetrical location and distribution. When diagnosing, it is important to pay attention to how the elements are located in relation to each other, signs of pain and redness.

In the diagnosis of many diseases, it is important to study the cellular composition of the fluid inside the bladder, it is necessary to find acontolytic cells from the surface of erosion from the resulting grease and carry out a cytological examination.

Secondary injury elements: erosion - resulting from injury resulting from rupture of the papule, the opening of the cavity formed by the death of the epithelium, resulting from a violation of the epithelial whole. Erosion caused by injury is called excoriation. Erosion ends without forming a scar.

The body is formed from the construction of exudate substance, which is separated from bubbles, microabstresses, cracks and wounds. The color of the body depends on the composition of the exudate (serous, purulent, hemorrhagic). Tumors and tumor derivatives found in the tumor or oral cavity are pathological enlargements from the compaction of cells unsuitable for physiological activity. Specific, that is, both qualitative and quantitative changes of tumors and cells in relation to regulatory cells are observed under the influence of a number of factors.

A tumor can develop in any tissue or organ of a person. It will consist of nodes of a circular or oval shape, a solid derivative that grows larger like a cauliflower shape. Tumors located in the mucous membrane shell in most cases get injured.

³ K.Bakhodirov. Diagnosis and diagnosis in internal diseases, Tashkent 1993.

Angiomatous vessels are a violation of the innate physiological activity of the vessels, an increase in size or an excessive expansion of the capillaries (teleangiectasia), which is a consequence of a specific deficiency in the formation of a mechanism in the process of the appearance of an organism and a process of perception accompanied by pathological changes, such as during the

When morphologically examining the elements in patients, it is important to once again determine whether it is diffuse, its symmetrical location, the appearance of the elements in the patient in relation to one type, or whether they are rashes of different appearance.

When examining a morphological element, it is necessary for us to know its color, shape appearance, location and consistency relative to the surrounding tissue, how deep it is located. Based on the request and vision from the patient, we clarify the periodicity of each rash, whether it appears from time to time, how long it keeps its shape, whether a severe scar remains and what is characteristic. An important place for diagnosis is occupied by the importance of isomorphous reaction (Kebner's symptom), the appearance of new primary elements, the liquid composition of the element, its damaging role, exogenous factors of the skin or mucous membrane (removal, swelling, peeling, pouring, exposure to sunlight).

In some cases, in order to determine the belonging of one or another type of morphological element, a special examination method, "vitropressiya" - with a glass or object mirror, the wound is pressed and twisted clockwise; in this, depending on the staining of the wound, its fluid (mass) inside is determined. If, on the basis of etiology, suspicion of an infectious descriptive disease arises, bacterioscopic, in some cases bacteriological diagnosis is carried out, in which the material from the examined derivative element is obtained. In some types of diseases, it is necessary to carry out an examination to find the composition of the bladder fluid, the cytological composition of the greases, the elements of the ocontolytic cell on erosion. Another of the complex aspects of Dermatology is that in most diseases, a rash of similar signs is observed, regardless of its etiological and pathogenetic origin. In such cases, it is necessary to use a histological type of examination - the biopsy method. For examination, a partial fracture of both the wound and the healthy tissue is necessary. Histological comparison of cells provides the basis for diagnosis.

For the last 15-20 years, in order to diagnose diseases of the oral mucosa and dermatosis, the immune status is important in the pathogenesis of the disease, as well as the method of mediated and direct immunofluorescence (RIF), such as the examination of autoimmune mechanisms, is being used. The Mediated (first) method identifies circulatory immunoglobulins (antitelo), Class A, M, and G, and the direct (second) method identifies different tissue component, class A, M, Class G immunoglobulins in fibrin. Such reef reactions are used in the comparative diagnosis of bladder diseases from Red rune and other diseases.

It is necessary to pay close attention to the results of a general examination of a whole organism, in which changes are observed in the mucous membrane and lip of the oral cavity. It is necessary to investigate the central and peripheral nervous system, including dermatography, pain and temperature sensitivity, substance exchange detection, internal organs, blood-creating organs, internal secretion organs, cardiovascular system, that is, the systems of the organism that occupy an important place in the pathogenesis of dermatostomatological diseases.

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